

Study on edible arthropods available in the markets of Guwahati and evaluation of their nutritional value.

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Abstract

A market survey on edible arthropods was conducted in two different markets of Guwahati and 7 different edible arthropod species were found. A comparative analysis on the tissue and hemolymph protein has been conducted to find their nutritional value. In the enumeration *Sartoriana trilobata* (fresh water crab) showed high protein content in both tissue and hemolymph. In the availability and popularity level, it was found that *Sartoriana trilobata* and *Fenneropenaeus indicus* (common Indian shrimp) seems to be having very high popularity and availability in the market throughout the year than the other species.

Key words

Edible arthropods, Protein content, Hemolymph, Alternative food resource.

Introduction

In the new world scenario, increasing human population has high impact on food resources, because with the increasing population, food resources are not increasing simultaneously. Many developing and underdeveloped countries facing difficulties to provide sufficient nutritive food to their population which leads to malnutrition of their citizen^{1,2}. Therefore, world is focusing on searching of alternative food resource, which are easily available, cheap and very nutritive. Such category of food can be filled by some lower group invertebrates like edible insects, molluscans and shellfish items³. Such kind of food are consumed by native tribes of India form a decade, they are easily available and very low in cost. In north east India, there are many indigenous tribes taking invertebrates as food due to their medicinal and nutritional properties⁴.

Though eating of such food is not common to all parts or the world, but it has been a part of human existence. By scientific study of the nutritional value of this alternative food resource awareness can be raised among the people and it can draw attention to the policy makers and stakeholders towards the potential growth of edible alternative food sectors and on their research and development⁵.

Material and method

Study area:

Study about different invertebrates consumed by people of Asaam was conducted on Beltola and Uzan Bazar Market, Guwahati, Assam. The city is located in a latitude of 26.10° N and 91.58°E. Sample was collected from that 2 market itself. All the samples used in the study were collected at their ideal stage of their life cycle at which they are consumed by people. The sample were collected during the month of late January to first week of May 2024. (Map is collected from Kashyap *et al.*,2010 with slight modification)⁶.

Fig1: Map of Guwahati City showing location of Beltola Bazar and Uzan Bazar.

Insect collection:

Insects were collected from the two market and were identified and classified with valid taxonomic key. The specimens were preserved by using standard methods and identified later on ny comparing with the other specimens ⁷.

Chemicals:

All chemicals were provided by Department of Zoology, USTM and supplied by North East Chemicals, Panbazar, Guwahati, Assam.

Preparation of tissue homogenate:

1 gm of body tissue was taken and 10 ml of Phosphate buffer solution was added to it. Tissue homogenate was prepared by using mortar and pestle. Tissue homogenate was centrifuged in 6000 rpm. Supernatant was collected and used as a tissue source for biochemical analysis.

Hemolymph extraction:

1ml of disposable hypodermic syringe fitted with 24-gauge needle after rinsing with anticoagulant (1% Sodium citrate) was used for withdrawal of hemolymph. The needle was carefully inserted into pericardial region

through the intersegmental membranes between the cephalothorax and the first abdominal segment in prawn and shrimp but in crab hemolymph was collected from the segment between claws. Apart from prawn, shrimp and crab, hemolymph was collected from other invertebrates by following the methodology of Zeng *et al.*, 2018 and Niu *et al.*, 2023^{7,8}.

Protein estimation:

In both cases, tissue protein and hemolymph protein were estimated by using Lowry's *et al.*, 1951 method⁹. Calibration curve prepared with different concentration (0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8 and 1 mg/ml) of BSA as standard.

Carbohydrate estimation:

Estimation of carbohydrate was done by using Anthrone method¹⁰.

Lipid estimation:

The total lipid was estimated using chloroform methanol method¹¹.

Statistical analysis:

All the results are statistically analyzed using Mean and Standard Error of Mean.

Result and Discussion

Collected Invertebrates:

In the study, 7 species from 4 (Hemiptera, Isoptera, Coleoptera and Decapoda) different orders are collected which includes, Giant water bug, Termite, Beetle, wood worm, prawn, shrimps and Crab. All the collected invertebrates are listed with their common name, scientific name, order and photographs after collection in Table 1.

Availability and popularity of collected specimen:

In the current study it was found that the availability of the specimens is always depending upon the season. Specimens like Indian white shrimp and freshwater crab are available in every season but species like wood

borer and termite are not frequently seen. Specimens like Water bug and diving beetle and monsoon river shrimp are highly available during monsoon. As per the market survey it was documented that freshwater crab and Indian white shrimp was the highly popular among the market dwellers of the study area (Table 2).

Estimation of total tissue protein in collected arthropods:

In the present study, the estimated tissue protein in the collected arthropods showed the presence of good amount of protein. The highest tissue protein was showed by freshwater crab (*S. trilobata*) in an amount of 0.606 mg/ g of tissue while, termite (*Macrotermes sp.*) showed less amount of protein (0.176mg/gm of tissue). Result of tissue protein for all the collected specimen was listed in Table 2.

Estimation of total hemolymph protein content of collected arthropods:

In the hemolymph protein estimation, the highest value was again showed by freshwater crab (*S. trilobata*) in an amount of 1.665mg/ml, while lowest value was showed by diving beetle (*Cybister tripunctatus*) in an amount of 0.989 mg/ml. Results for all the specimens are listed in Table 4.

From the result, it was evident that all the arthropod species collected in the study are having impressive amount of tissue protein. The hemolymph protein is a bit less than the tissue protein but having enormous food value. In a similar experiment Li, 2015 has documented the potential of insect protein and lipid as a food source¹⁰. The study provide insight in the possible use of insect as human food. Similarly, Maheshwarudu, 1991 and Fredrick *et al.*, 2013 has studied on the protein content of different insect's hemolymph and found that it is a very protein reach component and can be studied on their peptide levels^{11,12}. Again in an another study on entomophagy, lots of mineral contents found in many edible insects having health benefits^{13,14}. Study on medicinal property of insect protein has been also found in many documentation , explaining the anticancer potential of many insect protein^{15,16}.

Table 1: Table showing collected specimen's common name, Scientific name, Order and stage of consumption with photographs.

Common name	Scientific name	Order	Consumption as	Photograph
Giant water bug	<i>Lethocerus indicus</i>	Hemiptera	Adult/nymph	
Termite	<i>Macrotermes spp.</i>	Isoptera	Adult	
Wood borer	<i>Batocera horsefieldi</i>	Coleoptera	Larvae	
Diving beetle	<i>Cybister tripunctatus</i>	Coleoptera	Adult/Nymph	
Indian white shrimp	<i>Fenneropenaeus indicus</i>	Decapoda	Adult	

Monsoon river prawn	<i>Macrobrachium malcolmsonii</i>	Decapoda	Adult	
Freshwater crab	<i>Sartoriana trilobata</i>	Decapoda	Adult	

Table 2: Table showing market survey result of availability in the market and popularity of arthropod species among consumers.

Species name	Availabilty	Popularity
<i>Lethocerrus indicus</i>	+++	+++
<i>Macrotermes spp.</i>	+	++
<i>Batocera horsefieldi</i>	+	++
<i>Cybister tripunctatus</i>	+	++
<i>Fenneropenaeus indicus</i>	++++	++++
<i>Macrobrachium malcolmsonii</i>	++	++++
<i>Sartoriana trilobata</i>	++++	++++

(+= Low, += Moderate, +++ =High, +++++Very high)

Table3: Table showing hemolymph protein content of collected specimens.

Species name	Protein content (mg/g)
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<i>Lethocerrus indicus</i>	0.462±0.0088
<i>Macrotermes spp.</i>	0.176±0.0062
<i>Batocera horsefieldi</i>	0.203±0.0086
<i>Cybister tripunctatus</i>	0.285±0.0078
<i>Fenneropenaeus indicus</i>	0.443±0.0069
<i>Macrobrachium malcolmsonii</i>	0.452±0.0069
<i>Sartoriana trilobata</i>	0.606±0.0529

N=5 (Mean±SEM)

Table4: Table showing tissue protein, lipid and carbohydrate content of collected specimens.

Species name	Protein content (mg/g)	Carbohydrate content (mg/G)	Lipid content (mg/g)
<i>Lethocerrus indicus</i>	214.23±2.34	133.00±4.65	29.00±3.61
<i>Macrotermes spp.</i>	145.55± 3.48	186.33±5.34	43.22±4.42
<i>Batocera horsefieldi</i>	123.32±1.34	174.26±4.34	28.10±3.33
<i>Cybister tripunctatus</i>	145.33±2.28	165.37±3.33	39.23±2.11
<i>Fenneropenaeus indicus</i>	189.19±1.89	65.90±4.78	49.51±5.34
<i>Macrobrachium malcolmsonii</i>	194.39±3.25	79.00±5.67	72.12±2.14
<i>Sartoriana trilobata</i>	165.65±2.86	72.34±2.34	71.56±3.56

N=5 (Mean±SEM)

Conclusion:

Alternative food resource is a very important area of research in today's scenario. They are enriched with different essential nutrients and a proper documentation is necessary to aware people as well as health and food industries. This area can be utilized to get new food resource having high food value and low coast. Traditionally many ethnic tribes of India used these food resources as food and as a supplement having medicinal and health benefits. Recently, the pharmaceutical sector has extracted protein from many arthropods and are being

examined against many health-related ailments. Proper Scientific study is needed to unveil all the benefits of these food resources.

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